

BRAZILIAN PRIMES WHICH ARE ALSO SOPHIE GERMAIN PRIMES

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Abstract

We disprove a conjecture of Schott that no Brazilian prime is a Sophie Germain prime. We compute all counterexamples up to 10^{46} . We prove conditional asymptotics for the number of Brazilian Sophie Germain primes up to x .

1. Introduction

The term “Brazilian numbers” comes from the 1994 Iberoamerican Mathematical Olympiad [8] in Fortaleza, Brazil, in a problem proposed by the Mexican math team.¹ They became a topic of lively discussion on the forum mathematiques.net. Bernard Schott [5] summarized the results in the standard reference on Brazilian numbers.

Definition 1. A *Brazilian number* n is an integer whose base- b representation has all the same digits for some $1 < b < n - 1$.

In other words, n is Brazilian if and only if $n = m \left(\frac{b^q - 1}{b - 1} \right) = mb^{q-1} + \dots + mb + m$, with $q \geq 2$. These numbers are [A125134](https://oeis.org/A125134) in the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (OEIS).

A *Brazilian prime* (or “prime repunit”) is a Brazilian number that is prime; by necessity, $m = 1$ and $q \geq 3$. See [A085104](https://oeis.org/A085104) in the OEIS for the sequence of Brazilian primes. In 2010, Schott [5] conjectured that no Brazilian prime is also a Sophie Germain prime.

¹The term appears as “sensato” in the original problem [6]. The authors are puzzled by the discrepancy with [8].

Sophie Germain discovered her eponymous primes while trying to prove Fermat’s Last Theorem; her work was one of the first major steps towards a proof.

Definition 2. A *Sophie Germain prime* is a prime p such that $2p + 1$ is also prime.

Germain showed that if p is such a prime, then there are no non-zero integers x, y, z , not divisible by p , such that $x^p + y^p = z^p$. If p is a Sophie Germain prime, then we say that $2p + 1$ is a *safe prime*.

It is conjectured that there are infinitely many Sophie Germain primes, but the claim is still unproven. The Bateman-Horn conjecture [1] implies that the number of Sophie Germain primes less than x is asymptotic to $2C \frac{x}{\log^2 x}$, where

$$C = \prod_{p>2} \frac{p(p-2)}{(p-1)^2} \approx 0.660161.$$

See [3] for further information about Sophie Germain primes.

2. Enumerating Counterexamples

To aid our search, we use a few lemmas.

Lemma 1. *If $p = \frac{b^q-1}{b-1}$ is a Brazilian prime, then q is an odd prime.*

Proof. Recall $x^q - 1$ is divisible by the m th cyclotomic polynomial $\Phi_m(x)$ for $m|q$; therefore p can only be prime if q is also prime. Note that $q > 2$ because $b < p - 1$, so q is an odd prime. □

The preceding lemma is also Corollary 4.1 of Schott [5].

Lemma 2. *If p is a Brazilian prime and a Sophie Germain prime, then $p \equiv q \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ and $b \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.*

Proof. If p is a Sophie Germain prime, then 3 cannot divide the safe prime $2p + 1$, so p cannot be congruent to 1 (mod 3). The number 3 is not Brazilian, so $p \neq 3$ and thus $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

If $3|b$, then

$$p = b^{q-1} + b^{q-2} + \dots + b + 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3},$$

which is a contradiction. Lemma 1 states that q is an odd prime, so if $b \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, a contradiction. We conclude that $b \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, so that $q \equiv p \pmod{3}$, and therefore $q \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. □

For $q = 5$, we use a modification of the technique described in [7] to compute a table of length-5 Brazilian primes up to 10^{46} . We will describe this computation in full in a forthcoming paper [2]. Of these, 104890280 are Sophie Germain primes.

The smallest is $28792661 = 73^4 + 73^3 + 73^2 + 73 + 1$. We very easily prove the primality of Sophie Germain primes with the Pocklington-Lehmer test.

For $q \geq 11$, we very quickly enumerate all possibilities for $b \leq 10^{46/(q-1)}$. We find 22 Brazilian Sophie Germain primes for $q = 11$, and none for larger q . (We have $q < \log_2 10^{46} + 1 < 154$.) The smallest is

$$14781835607449391161742645225951 = 1309^{10} + 1309^9 + \dots + 1309 + 1.$$

While we disprove Schott’s conjecture, we do have a related proposition.

Proposition 1. *The only Brazilian prime which is a safe prime is 7.*

Proof. If $p = b^{q-1} + \dots + b + 1$ is a safe prime, then $\frac{p-1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}(b^{q-1} + \dots + b)$ must also be prime. This expression, however, is divisible by $\frac{b(b+1)}{2}$, which is only prime when $b = 2$ and $p = 7$. □

The list of Brazilian Sophie Germain primes is [A306845](#) in the OEIS. The first few counterexamples were also discovered by Giovanni Resta and Michel Marcus; see the comments for [A085104](#).

3. Conditional Results

The infinitude of Brazilian Sophie Germain primes, as well as the asymptotic number of them, is the consequence of well-known conjectures.

Proposition 2. *Assuming Schnizel’s Hypothesis H, there are infinitely many Brazilian Sophie Germain primes.*

Proof. Recall that Hypothesis H [4] says that any set of polynomials, whose product is not identically zero modulo any prime, is simultaneously prime infinitely often. Take our two polynomials to be $f_0(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ and $f_1(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 3$. Then $f_0(b)$ is Brazilian and $f_1(b) = 2f_0(b) + 1$. Rather than checking congruences, it suffices to note the existence of the above primes of this form to see that the conditions of Hypothesis H are satisfied. □

The Bateman-Horn Conjecture [1] implies a more precise statement about the number of Brazilian Sophie Germain primes.

Proposition 3. *For an odd prime q , let $\Phi_q(x)$ be the q th cyclotomic polynomial. Assuming the Bateman-Horn Conjecture, the number of values of $b < x$ such that $\Phi_q(b)$ and $2\Phi_q(b) + 1$ are simultaneously prime is 0 or $\sim C_q \frac{x}{\log^2 x}$, for some positive constant C_q , depending on whether $\Phi_q(b)(2\Phi_q(b) + 1)$ is identically zero modulo some prime p .*

Proof. This follows immediately from the Bateman-Horn conjecture, with $C_q = \left(\prod_p \frac{1-N(p)/p}{(1-1/p)^2} \right) / q^2$, where $N(p)$ is the number of roots of $\Phi_q(b)(2\Phi_q(b)+1)$ modulo p . \square

Corollary 1. *Assuming the Bateman-Horn Conjecture, the number of Brazilian Sophie Germain primes up to x is $\sim C \frac{x^{1/4}}{\log^2 x}$, for some C .*

Proof. To find the number of Brazilian Sophie Germain primes less than y of the form $\Phi_q(b)$ for a fixed q , we apply the preceding proposition, substituting $x = y^{1/(q-1)}$, and get $\sim C'_q \frac{y^{1/(q-1)}}{\log^2 y}$, with $C'_q = C_q(q-1)^2$. We sum over all $q \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ and notice that the $q = 5$ term dominates. We can thus take $C = C'_5$. \square

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